

THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE REALIZATION OF THE STRENGTH
OF GLASS FIBERS IN THE COMPOSITES

M.S. Aslanova

All-Union Scientific-Research Institute of
Glass Fiber and Glass Reinforced Plastics
Moscow, USSR

On the basis of glass fibers of different chemical composition the factors affecting the realization of their strength in composite materials were examined.

It has been shown that during tensile and especially compression tests of glass reinforced plastics the high strength of glass fibers is not realized in full measure.

It has been ascertained that modulus of elasticity of the composition has dependence on modulus of elasticity of glass fiber.

The given data show that strength and modulus of elasticity of quartz fibers and magnesia-alumosilicate fibers are best realized in the composites, on condition of optimum schemes of reinforcement and rational technology of their production.